
PROTEST FOR SOME, DISRUPTION FOR THE REST? NEED FOR STRIKING A BALANCE BETWEEN TWO FACETS OF THE SAME COIN

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ABSTRACT

Constitution of India guarantees the right to free speech and expression as well as right to assemble peaceably without arms. Following these ideals, we get our right to protest and register dissent and discontent towards the government. The authors in this article will show the various aspects of right to protest and the restrictions which come along with it. Starting with a historical background on the protest movements, article explains the constitutional and statutory dimensions that are associated with the right to protest. Further, the article elaborates on the judicial pronouncements that have upheld this right for a long time. Authors then go on to explain how this right is not absolute and an unfettered access to it is not available to everyone. The article also deals with the aspect that how this right is not available to certain classes of society and the classification is done on the certain professional basis by the courts from time to time. The rights of people protesting and rights of the rest of the public must be in harmoniously interpreted so as to serve the greater interest of the society. The article then goes on to discuss the recent Shaheen Bagh judgement and Supreme Court's order staying the operation of recent farm laws. Further, by citing example of the India against corruption movement the essay deals with the aspect that how these protests ensure a sense of accountability in a democracy. The authors also try to highlight the issues that how by applying the dictum of 'Protests at designated places' will dilute the concept of the right to protest guaranteed by the constitution. On a concluding note, it is also highlighted that as the rights are not absolute and in such situations are often in conflict with rights of individuals *inter se*, the Apex Court should consider this while disposing of the review petition for the Shaheen Bagh verdict.

Keywords: Protests, Democracy, Restrictions, Designated Place, Shaheen Bagh, Farm Laws.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the turn of the decade, it is worth noting that India is facing a crisis. To put it more specifically, the backbone of the nation i.e., farmers hailing from various regions, across India are protesting since November 26, 2020 on the outskirts of National Capital and at various other places. The same is owing to the laws recently passed by the Parliament concerning the agriculture sector. Protests in any democracy are the way through which the people constantly remind their political masters that Indian democracy is based on the principle of inclusiveness and accommodating all kinds of diversity. Right to disagree with the government and its policies is an intrinsic part of the Right to Freedom of Speech and Expression guaranteed by most democracies to its citizens. Right to Protest forms an important facet of this right made available to the denizens in any democratic society. There are many different ways to express one's disagreement with the government policies and decisions. Some people choose to express themselves using the media channels such as print media, social media, etc. but one of the most common practices to express one's disagreement is to resort to means of a peaceful protest, employing methods of picketing, sit-ins, *dharnas*, blockades, *hartals*, *bandhs*, etc. Indians have been familiar with all these methods since colonial rule. These methods helped them to give vent to their opinions against the policies of the colonial masters. Be it the Civil Disobedience Movement or the Satyagraha or the Chipko Movement it is evident that a peaceful protest goes a long way in voicing one's opinion. Recently, India has seen various citizens and groups protesting against the Citizenship Amendment Act¹ (*hereinafter* as CAA), Farm laws², extending reservation benefits³ to certain sections of society, and the proposed NRC⁴ to name a few. The authors will deal with the various aspects of development of Right to Protest in Indian democracy. This piece also tries to deal with recent developments in the said field and the approach of the judiciary to harmonise the rights of the citizens *inter se*.

¹Special Correspondent, 'Protest Against CAA in Ludhiana' The Hindu (Chandigarh, 9 March 2020), <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/protest-against-caa-in-ludhiana/article31026314.ece>.

²'Farmers Protest Against Farm Bills in Many States' The Hindu Business Line (New Delhi, 25 September 2020), <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/economy/agri-business/farmers-protest-against-farm-bills-in-many-states/article32698655.ece>.

³Harsha Kumari Singh, 'Rajasthan Gujjars Block Tracks in Reservation Protest, Train Schedule Hit' NDTV (1 November 2020), <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/protest-for-reservation-in-rajasthan-will-continue-says-gujjar-leader-2319012>.

⁴Tiruchi Bureau, 'Agitation in Protest Against CAA, NPR, NRC' The Hindu (Tiruchirapalli, 18 March 2020), <https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Tiruchirapalli/agitation-in-protest-against-cao-npr-nrc/article31101366.ece>.

2. LEGACY OF PROTESTS IN INDIA

The way people protest in India is influenced a lot by our historical protest movements and also due to the contemporary issues prevailing in our society. The roots of our present lie in our past. Indians have been subjected to repressive, regressive and discriminatory practices at the hands of earlier rulers as well as the colonial rule of British, and thus the struggle. Socio-religious movements as well as liberation movements have been of huge significance when it comes to realising the various dimensions of protest and dissent. From the reformist movements led by Arya Samaj, Brahmo Samaj etc. for Hindus and Wahabi movement and Ahmadiya Movement led by Indian Muslims to the independence struggle under the aegis of Congress party since 1885, India has seen it all. Out of various modes and methods to protest the Gandhian technique was considered to be genius. Our last phase of nationalist movement from 1919 to 1947 was majorly guided by it. Peaceful protest on a massive scale was the foundation of this technique. The Non-Cooperation Movement, Civil Disobedience Movement and the Quit India Movement were the product of this technique. The Gandhian technique is motivated by the non-violence philosophy and even if there was a section, who did not believe in it, accepted it as a political expediency. The historical legacy of protest movements have left an imprint on the minds of Indian people. This is the reason that in today's world, a peaceful protest goes a long way in making the government submit to the terms and conditions of the protestors.

3. CONSTITUTIONAL & STATUTORY DIMENSIONS

The Right to Protest is guaranteed under the Constitution of India (*hereinafter* as Constitution) by way of right to free speech and expression⁵ and right to assemble peaceably without arms⁶ but the same is subjected to restrictions under Article 19(2)⁷ & 19(3)⁸ respectively. With certain rights come certain duties. Accordingly, Article 51-A(i)⁹ states that it is the duty of citizens to abjure violence and safeguard public property, thus the same ideals must be kept in mind while organizing protests. But a question arises as to where do we draw the line of the restrictions imposed and the liberty of exercising these rights. One must always keep in mind while exercising their rights is that they must not transgress into the rights of others and become an

⁵ INDIA CONSTI. art. 19, cl. (1)(a).

⁶ INDIA CONSTI. art. 19, cl. (1)(b).

⁷ INDIA CONSTI. art. 19, cl. (2).

⁸ INDIA CONSTI. art. 19, cl. (3).

⁹ INDIA CONSTI, art. 51-A, cl. (i).

inconvenience to them. Both, Article 19(1)(a)¹⁰ and Article 19(1)(b)¹¹ form an integral part of the right to demonstration. It can be seen that when people choose the picketing, sit-ins, *dharnas*, blockades, *hartals*, *bandhs*, etc. to show their discontent or dissent they often end up causing a lot of trouble for the people who do not associate themselves with the protest and just want to continue their daily routine. Section 144¹² of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (*hereinafter* as CrPC) is also an example of the fact that the above stated rights are not absolute and whoever is found in violation of this section can be punished under Section 188¹³ of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. However, this goes without saying that this tool is supposed to be used only to prevent any sort of obstruction, annoyance and injury to any person lawfully employed, or danger to human life, health or safety, or a disturbance of the public tranquillity, or a riot, of an affray.¹⁴ More often than not this discretion is exercised by the Magistrate when he is satisfied that not doing so will put the public safety in jeopardy, and the order must reflect that the Magistrate has applied his mind and taken into consideration the existing factors for such action.¹⁵ Therefore, a general order might be necessary in case of protest and such general order against the general public is justified but if the action is too general the order may be questioned by appropriate remedies for which there is ample provision in law.¹⁶ Article 32¹⁷ or Article 226¹⁸ of the Constitution can be invoked if there is any infringement of fundamental rights by way of such executive order under Section 144 of CrPC.¹⁹ Supreme Court in *Madhu Limaye* case²⁰ was correct in stating that any danger or disturbance sought to be prevented by Section 144 of CrPC must be construed under the light of clauses (2) to (6) of Article 19 of the Constitution and when so construed “must assume sufficiently grave proportions to bring the matter within the interests of public order” or general public or any other matters specified in clauses (2) to (6) of Article 19 of the Constitution.²¹ Even Article 33²² of the Constitution enables the Parliament of India to make laws which can modify the application of rights conferred by Part III of the Constitution in application to the armed forces of the country, forces

¹⁰Supra note 5.

¹¹Supra note 6.

¹² Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, §144, No. 2 of 1974, Acts of Parliament, 1973 (India).

¹³ Indian Penal Code, 1860, §188, No. 45 of 1860, Acts of Parliament, 1860 (India).

¹⁴ Babulal Parate v. State of Bombay, AIR 1960 SC 51; Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India, (2019) SCC Online SC 1725.

¹⁵ B Linga Murthy v. B Hussain Saheb, (1979) CriLJ 1147.

¹⁶ Madhu Limaye v. Sub-divisional Magistrate, Monghyr, AIR 1971 SC 2486.

¹⁷ INDIA CONST. art. 32.

¹⁸ INDIA CONST. art. 226.

¹⁹ Gulam Abbas v. State of UP, (1982) 1 SCR 1077.

²⁰ Supra note 16.

²¹ Gopalji Prasad v. State of Sikkim, (1981) CriLJ 60.

²² INDIA CONST. art. 33.

charged with maintaining public order and persons involved in intelligentsia. However, government servants are excluded from this category and their right to freedom of expression cannot be restricted without satisfying the test of Article 19 of the Constitution. Thus, Supreme Court in *Kameshwar Prasad & Ors. v. State of Bihar & Ors.*²³ ruled that government servants can participate in demonstrations so long as they do not result in breakdown of public order. The talk about all the restrictions is important as they make sure that the larger public interest and purpose is served when exercising certain rights, recognised by one or few laws, conflict with other rights or tend to endanger public peace, tranquillity and harmony.²⁴

4. JUDICIAL PRONOUNCEMENTS

The Supreme Court in *Ramlila Maidan* case²⁵ stated that any arbitrary action by the executive or the legislature cannot divest the citizens of this land of their fundamental right to assembly and peaceful protest. This right is not absolute and it also comes with certain duties.²⁶ More often than not certain professions even resort to strike to express themselves. However, there exists a stark difference between demonstrations through the means of peaceful protest and a strike. In *Radhey Shyam v. PMG, Nagpur*²⁷, the Apex Court ruled that the Constitution of India does not provide for fundamental right to go on strike. One of the most common ways of protesting is calling for *bandhs* or *hartals*. It should not come as news to people that such tools were effective in a totalitarian regime and not in the present-day scenario. The case of *Bharat Kumar K. Palicha & Ors. v. Union of India & Ors.*²⁸ declared *bandhs* as unconstitutional as they violate the rights of people with respect to travelling and practicing their trade. The reasoning behind the *Bharat Kumar* case that was put forth is people's right to protest is not superior to other people's fundamental rights, and one should not be practised on the cost of the other. These *bandhs* not only disrupt the lives of people but also cause the nation a great loss.²⁹ However, an appeal against the aforementioned judgement was dismissed by the Supreme Court. The Supreme Court in *James Martin v. State of Kerala*³⁰ ruled that taking a lenient or soft approach for such offenders would prove as ruffling the feathers of rule of law thereby posing a challenge to the public order and peace. Following this, Patna High Court in

²³ *Kameshwar Prasad & Ors. v. State of Bihar & Ors.*, AIR 1962 SC 1166.

²⁴ *In re Ramlila Maidan incident*, (2012) 5 SCC 1.

²⁵ *Id.*

²⁶ *Anita Thakur v. State of J&K & Ors.*, (2016) SCC Online SC 814.

²⁷ *Radhey Shyam v. PMG, Nagpur*, AIR 1965 SC 311.

²⁸ *Bharat Kumar K. Palicha & Ors. v. Union of India & Ors.*, AIR 1997 Ker 291.

²⁹ *Id.* ¶ 18.

³⁰ *James Martin v. State of Kerala*, (2004) 2 SCC 203.

*Ranchi Bar Association v. State of Bihar*³¹ prohibited parties from declaring *bandhs* and compelling people to give up their fundamental rights. It is the duty of the State to ensure that there exists no apprehension to the fundamental rights of citizens and in case of breach of such duty the State must be held liable to pay compensation.³² Karnataka High Court recently ordered the State Government to recover losses caused due to the *bandh* to be paid to roadside vendors and small traders.³³ The Court in *People's Council for Social Justice v. State of Kerala*³⁴ ruled that freedom of association and assembly are linked to freedom of speech and expression. However, these should be exercised without causing injury or annoyance to others. In respect of procession and street marches, the authorities have got the right to impose reasonable restrictions to protect equal rights of all users of roads. In *Communist Party of India (M) & Ors. v. Bharat Kumar & Ors.*³⁵, the Supreme Court ruled that fundamental rights of the people as a whole cannot be subservient to the claim of the fundamental rights of an individual or only a section of the people. The Courts have adopted such an approach where the rights of protestors are balanced vis-à-vis the public at large and are sub-serving the public interest.

5. RIGHT TO PROTEST NOT AVAILABLE TO CERTAIN PROFESSIONALS

We also have laws in place regulating the discretion to go on a strike. Article 33 of the Constitution³⁶ is one such example. Not only this Section 3(4)³⁷ of the Essential Services Maintenance Act, 1968 enables the Central Government to restrict strikes in essential services to safeguard public interest. There are certain professions which exist with the sole purpose to serve the public, and the legal profession is one of them. Thus, in *Ex-Capt. Harish Uppal v. Union of India and Another*³⁸, the Court declared that lawyers have no right to go on strike, and went on to observe that if they want to show their discontent over certain issues then they will have to do so outside the court premises through peaceful measures without hindering the course of justice. The reasoning behind the judgement is that there exists a right to speedy trial

³¹*Ranchi Bar Association v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1999 Pat 169.

³² Id ¶ 19; *D.K. Basil v. State of West Bengal*, (1997) 1 SCC 416.

³³Rintu Mariam Biju, 'Recover Losses Caused to Small Traders during Bandhs from Organisers/ Political Parties: Karnataka High Court to State Government' (Bar and Bench, 7 December 2020), <https://www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/recover-losses-small-traders-political-parties-bandhs-karnataka-high-court>.

³⁴*People's Council for Social Justice v. State of Kerala*, AIR 1997 Ker 309.

³⁵*Communist Party of India (M) & Ors. v. Bharat Kumar & Ors.*, (1998) 1 SCC 201.

³⁶ *Supra* note 22.

³⁷ Essential Services Maintenance Act, 1968, § 3(4), No. 59 of 1968, Acts of Parliament, 1968 (India).

³⁸*Ex-Capt. Harish Uppal v. Union of India & Anr.*, (2003) 2 SCC 45, see also *District Bar Association, Dehradun v. Ishwar Shandilya and Ors.*, AIR 2020 SC 1412.

under the aegis of Article 21 of the Constitution³⁹ which cannot be compromised with.⁴⁰ Means to express discontent are many but the one that is done at the cost of others' fundamental rights should be avoided. Keeping that in mind, the 266th Law Commission of India Report⁴¹ recommended that instead of interfering with the administration of justice, grievances of lawyers can be tackled by creating an Advocates Grievances Redressal Committee headed by a Judicial Officer and in case of grievances arising out of the dispute with a Judicial Officer, Chief Justice of the concerned High Court must be approached. Also, various service rules formulated by the appropriate legislature under Article 309⁴² of the Constitution also say that the Government Servants do not have a right to strike as per the verdict of the Supreme Court in *Kameshwar Prasad & Ors. v. State of Bihar & Ors.*⁴³, as it is not a Fundamental Right. The aforementioned authorities provide an insight that how our Courts deal with the issue of right to protest when it is a matter of certain professionals, who are indispensable for the proper functioning of the administration in the society.

6. BALANCING THE RIGHT OF PROTESTORS VIS-A-VIS RIGHTS OF THE OTHER CITIZENS

The protests when organized also impact the daily life of other citizens who are not the participants in these demonstrations. The Indian judiciary in some of the landmark judgements has dealt with the issue of balancing the right of protest available to the citizens and the other rights available to the citizens who are non-participant in that particular demonstration. The authors would like to bring forth that if any such demonstration takes place, the main aim of the demonstrators is to seek attention of the officials and other fellow citizens to pay heed to their demands and join them respectively. For this most of the time techniques such as blocking of the roads, public highways, railway lines, ways to different public offices, or refusal to render services which a particular group is expected to perform, etc. are resorted to causing a disruption in the life of other fellow citizens. It is also witnessed in most of such cases that such protestors are often slapped with the Sedition charges under the Indian Penal Code⁴⁴ or the

³⁹INDIA CONST. art. 21.

⁴⁰Supra note 38 ¶ 17, 18; B.L. Wadhwa v. State (NCT of Delhi) and Ors., AIR 2000 Del 266 ¶ 30, 31.

⁴¹LAW COMMISSION OF INDIA, REPORT NO. 266: THE ADVOCATES ACT, 1961 (REGULATION OF LEGAL PROFESSION), 23 (2017).

⁴²INDIA CONST. art. 309.

⁴³Supra note 23.

⁴⁴ Archana Chaudhary, India wields Colonial Era Sedition law to detain Farm Protestors, (Bloomberg, Politics, 22 February 2021), <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-02-21/india-wields-colonial-era-sedition-law-to-detain-farm-protesters>.

frivolous charges under the anti-terror laws such as Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967.⁴⁵ Recently, the country has witnessed the protest over the issue of the CAA and the Farm Laws. These protests have also contributed to the developments in the jurisprudence relating to the right to protest available to the denizens of the land. The most recent and significant development in the jurisprudence of right to protest, especially the balancing aspect, are the cases of Shaheen Bagh protests and the protests against the farm laws. In the subsequent sections the essay discusses both these events and the contribution made by them and the observations of the Courts while dealing these matters.

7. OUTCOME OF SHAHEEN BAGH & FARM LAWS PROTESTS

A section of the citizens, aggrieved by the enactment of legislative amendment titled *Citizenship (Amendment) Act, 2019*⁴⁶, (*hereinafter as CAA*) filed petitions before Supreme Court under Article 32⁴⁷ of the Constitution of India, reprehending the constitutionality and legality of the impugned amendment, which are *sub-judice*. There have been protests against this law in Delhi and across the country. The original petition⁴⁸ was filed before the Delhi High Court which was disposed of where the Court in its final order⁴⁹ held that in such a situation no specific writ, order or direction can be issued as to how to handle the agitation or protest, or even the place of protest and traffic, as the same would be determined based on the ground reality and the wisdom of the police, especially where situation may change every 10 minutes. A petition⁵⁰ by the way of Special Leave⁵¹ relating to the same issue was also filed before the Supreme Court, against the Delhi High Court's Judgement. The grievance made in the petition was that the persons opposing the CAA and the National Register of Citizens, had adopted a method of protest resulting in the closure of the Kalindi Kunj-Shaheen Bagh stretch, including the Okhla underpass since 15.12.2019. An 'alarming situation' arose due to a 'blockade' of the road between the Kalindi Kunj and Mathura Road region, connecting Delhi-Noida-Faridabad.

⁴⁵ Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967, No. 37 of 1967, Acts of Parliament, 1967 (India).

⁴⁶ Citizenship (Amendment) Act, 2019, No. 47 of 2019, Acts of Parliament, 2019 (India).

⁴⁷ Supra note 17.

⁴⁸ Karan Tripathi, Shaheen Bagh Protests: Plea In Delhi HC Seeks Reopening Of Stretch Closed Due To Anti-CAA Stir (Live Law News Updates, 13 January 2020), www.livelaw.in/news-updates/shaheen-bagh-protests-plea-in-delhi-hc-seeks-reopening-of-stretch-closed-due-to-anti-cao-stir-151572?infinite-scroll=1.

⁴⁹ The final order was passed in the matter of Amit Sahni v. Commissioner of Police and Others, W.P. (C) No. 429 of 2020 on 14 January 2020. The copy of the final order could be accessed here http://164.100.69.66/jupload/dhc/DNP/judgement/14-01-2020/DNP14012020CW4292020_150454.pdf.

⁵⁰ Nilashish Chaudhary, Shaheen Bagh Protests : Plea In SC Challenges Closure Of Traffic (Live Law Top Stories, 20 January 2020), www.livelaw.in/top-stories/shaheen-bagh-protests-plea-in-sc-challenges-closure-of-traffic-151828.

⁵¹ INDIA CONST. art. 136.

It was contended that the public roads could not be permitted to be encroached upon in this manner and, thus, sought directions be issued to clear the same. The issue before the Court was that how and where protests of such kind can be carried on without getting the public ways being affected?

The Court after due consideration held that Article 19⁵², one of the cornerstones of the Constitution of India, confers upon its citizens two treasured rights, i.e., the right to freedom of speech and expression under Article 19(1)(a)⁵³ and the right to assemble peacefully without arms under Article 19(1)(b)⁵⁴ of the Constitution. These rights, in a conjoint reading, enable every citizen to assemble peacefully and protest against the actions or inactions of the State. The Court further added that these rights like others are also subject to certain reasonable restrictions, which, inter alia, pertaining to the interests of the sovereignty and integrity of India and public order, and, while appreciating the existence of the right to peaceful protest against a legislation or a policy of the government, it has to be made unequivocally clear that public ways and public spaces cannot be occupied in such a manner and that too indefinitely, thereby causing inconvenience to the public at large. Placing reliance on the *Mazdoor Kisan Shakti Sangathan*⁵⁵ case, the Court held that every fundamental right, whether of an individual or of a class, does not exist in isolation and has to be balanced with every other contrasting right. Also the court ruled that there was no fundamental right to hold a protest in a particular area. It was due to this, an attempt made by the court to reach a solution where the rights of protestors were to be balanced with that of commuters, thereby appointing interlocutors to report the ground reality to the court. In *Re Ramlila Maidan Incident*⁵⁶, the Court held that the rights which are involved here are subject to certain reasonable restrictions pertaining to interests of sovereignty and integrity of the Union and public order, along with the regulations by the police authorities in this regard. Referring to the *Himat Lal* case⁵⁷ the court reaffirmed that streets & public parks exist primarily for different purposes altogether. Limitless exercise of Freedom of expression and assembly in public street/way/highways must conform to social interests for which restrictions are designed to protect. Also, the shifting of protestors to a designated place amounts to a reasonable regulation and not exclusion by arbitrary means. Even Delhi High Court while granting Bail to Natasha Narwal, one of the prime suspects in the riots which

⁵² INDIA CONST. art. 19.

⁵³ Supra note 5.

⁵⁴ Supra note 6.

⁵⁵ *Mazdoor Kisan Shakti Sangathan v. Union of India & Ors.*, AIR 2018 SC 3476.

⁵⁶ Supra note 24.

⁵⁷ *Himat Lal K. Shah v. Commissioner of Police, Ahmedabad & Ors.*, (1973) 1 SCC 227.

happened in Delhi in February, 2020 on the account of CAA being enacted, noted that in an anxiety to suppress the dissent a fine distinction between the constitutionally guaranteed right to protest and terrorist activity seems to fade away and if this is allowed it will be the saddest day in the annals of the Indian Democracy.⁵⁸ But at the same time, in its order the Delhi High Court after relying upon the *Mazdoor Kisan Shakti Sangathan*⁵⁹ case remarked that the Government may prohibit any kind of public meetings, demonstrations, or protests on the Highways or streets for the purpose of avoiding any kind of nuisance or any disturbance to the traffic passing by, but the Government cannot close all the streets or every public area for any kind of public meeting, this action of the government will defeat the fundamental right of the citizens emanating from article 19(1) & article 19(2) of the *suprema lex*.⁶⁰ Furthermore, the Court observed that, even though the actions of the protestors amount to crossing the permissible limits of the Right to Protest guaranteed under the Constitution but this not gives unbridled power in the hands of the Government to book these protestors under the serious charges of terrorism and terror funding under the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967.⁶¹

After the verdict of Apex Court in the *Shaheen Bagh*⁶² matter, many of the petitions were moved in the court where the petitioners prayed for a similar kind of relief as prayed in the cited matter because in their opinion the on-going farmers' protest had caused a similar kind of blockade of the roads/highways leading to the national capital and thereby, infringing their fundamental right(s) envisaged in the Constitution i.e. to move freely throughout the territory of India and to carry on their trade and business. The Court while passing the order repelled the contentions of the Government that the court cannot stay the implementation of the laws enacted by the Parliament, by relying on an interim order passed by the court in the matter of *Dr. Jaishri Laxmanrao Patil v. The Chief Minister & Anr.*⁶³ The Apex Court in their interim order dated January 12th, 2021 stated that stifling a peaceful protest will not be right, but the stay of the implementation of the laws by the way of extraordinary order will give a sense of achievement of the purpose of such agitation and the participants of the agitation will appreciate the same. At the same time, they will be thinking to resume back their livelihood in

⁵⁸ Natasha Narwal v. State NCT of Delhi, Criminal Appeal No. 82 of 2021, ¶36.

⁵⁹ Supra Note 58.

⁶⁰ Supra Note 58, ¶ 25.

⁶¹ Supra Note 58, ¶ 35.

⁶² Amit Sahni v. Commissioner of Police & Ors., (2020) 10 SCC 439.

⁶³ Dr. Jaishri Laxmanrao Patil v. The Chief Minister & Anr., Civil Appeal No.3123 of 2020.

order to protect the health of theirs and others in such a situation where the effects of a global pandemic have not faded completely.

In its order, the Court stated a formation of the committee of expert members to resolve the issue; in the view of authors this move of the court signifies the element of the consultative process in democracy. The order of the Court clearly manifests that the Supreme Court is also a guardian of the Indian Democracy besides being the guardian of Indian Constitution. At the same time all the members of the committee formed are being identified by the protestors as persons favouring the enactment of laws. Hence, some of the farmers' organizations have asked the Court to remove them from the committee⁶⁴, after the recusal of one member from the same.⁶⁵ Also some of the Members from the Judiciary also remarked that the composition of committee must be made in such a way that at least one of the member is well versed with the realities at the ground.⁶⁶ But the remarks of the Hon'ble Court regarding the participants of this protest are quite surprising, as the Chief Justice of India himself remarked that the submission of one of the advocates regarding elders, women and children will not participate in the present protests will be taken on record.⁶⁷ This view of the court is heavily criticized as this makes a clear exclusion of a certain class of citizens (women and elderly people) from exercising an important right which the supreme law of this land guarantees them, without any discrimination. The authors would like to acknowledge the approach of the protestors in this agitation which is completely a non-violent one and this fact must be written in the annals of history of protest movements in India. The Committee appointed by the Supreme Court submitted its report to the Court sometime in March 2021.⁶⁸ It is pertinent to note that some of the citizens supporting the farm protestors were booked under the sedition charges by the

⁶⁴ Radhika Roy, Farmers' Union Requests Supreme Court To Remove The Remaining Members Of Committee Constituted To Resolve Deadlock Between Farmers and Govt (Live Law Top Stories, 16 January 2021), <https://www.livelaw.in/top-stories/farm-laws-farmers-union-supreme-court-bhartiya-kisan-union-lokshakti-delhi-police-168486>.

⁶⁵ Breaking- Bhupinder Singh Mann Recuses From Supreme Court Formed Committee To Negotiate On Farm Laws (Live Law News Network, 14 January 2021), <https://www.livelaw.in/top-stories/bhupinder-singh-mann-farm-laws-committee-supreme-court-168401>.

⁶⁶ There should be one member in the committee who knows the ground realities: Former HC judge Justice Rameshwar Singh Malik on farm laws protests (Bar and Bench News, 17 January 2021) <https://www.barandbench.com/news/justice-rameshwar-singh-malik-backs-farm-laws-protests>.

⁶⁷ "We Will Protects The Farmers' Land"- Supreme Court- Hearing On Farm Laws And Farmers Protest: Live-Updates (LiveLaw News Network, 12 January 2021), www.livelaw.in/top-stories/farm-laws-and-farmers-protest-live-updates-from-supreme-court-168294.

⁶⁸ Bar and Bench, Farm Laws Committee formed by Supreme Court submits report in sealed cover, (Bar and Bench Litigation News, 31 March 2021) <https://www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/farm-laws-committee-formed-by-supreme-court-submits-report-in-sealed-cover>.

government⁶⁹ and this was nothing but another move of the executive to silence the dissent of such people. It is to be kept in mind that mere protesting or showing any signs of protest cannot be termed as sedition as pronounced by the Apex Court in a couple of important cases.⁷⁰

But our Judiciary acting upon the core principles of the constitutional philosophy and democracy released such activists on Bail,⁷¹ by reiterating the dictum that ‘the offence of sedition cannot be invoked to minister the wounded vanity of the governments’, as pronounced in the case of *Niharendu Dutt Mazumdar v. Emperor*.⁷² One must be mindful of the fact that abovesaid Federal Court decision would have been a bold step in the times when it was pronounced, as those were the days of colonial rule and one could imagine how much courage it would have required to pronounce such decisions against the very government who still believed the epithet that ‘*Sun never sets on their (British) Empire*’.

8. ENSURING ACCOUNTABILITY

At times it is seen that the protests act as a safety valve in a democracy where the citizens get a right to express themselves against the policies of the government. Protests ensure healthy public participation in the decision making process as the minority opinion can be voiced using these means. Nowadays, we see that protesters are also using the various social media forums for carrying out protests. Trending hashtags on various social media platforms also cause the authorities to pay heed to the issues concerning the public at large. During protests public acts as a watchdog constantly monitoring government acts, providing feedback to the governments about their policies and actions after which the concerned government, through consultation, meetings and discussion, recognise and rectify its mistakes. In India, the protest under the banner “India Against Corruption movement” led to the enactment of the Lokpal and Lokayukta Act, 2013.⁷³ Many of such movements are an example that popular demonstrations can cause a change and public participation is the hallmark of a democracy.

⁶⁹ Raj Shekhar and Santosh Kumar, Delhi cops pick up 22-year-old Disha Ravi from Bengaluru for sedition in Greta toolkit case (Times of India, 15 February 2021), <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/delhi-cops-pick-up-22-year-old-girl-from-bengaluru-for-sedition-in-greta-toolkit-case/articleshow/80915712.cms>.

⁷⁰ Kedarnath Singh v. State of Bihar, AIR 1962 SC 955; Balwant Singh v. State of Punjab, (1995) 3 SCC 214.

⁷¹ State v. Disha A. Ravi, Bail Application No. 420 of 2021, the copy of the order can be accessed at https://www.livelaw.in/pdf_upload/disha-ravi-bail-order-asj-dharmender-rana-389605.pdf.

⁷² Niharendu Dutt Mazumdar v. Emperor, AIR 1942 FC 22.

⁷³ Lokpal and Lokayukta Act, 2013, No. 1 of 2014, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

9. COSTS INVOLVED OR THE CRITICAL SIDE OF THE PROTEST MOVEMENTS

Protest movements act as a catalyst bringing in Social and Political change in the society. One must be mindful of the fact that this change at times can cost the society on an economic front dearly. Across the globe these social unrests or protest movements have dented the economy on different scales. If at the macro level one needs to see, we can see the example of the protests of July 2019 in Hong Kong SAR and the yellow vest protests of 2018 in France which caused the reduction of about 1% in the GDP of these countries. These effects on GDP seem to be driven by sharp contractions in manufacturing and services (sectoral dimension), and consumption (demand dimension) sectors of the economy of these nations. Furthermore, these unrests have a potential of affecting the activity by lowering confidence and increasing uncertainty in the minds of the masses, which will in turn impact the economic growth of the nation.⁷⁴

The economic impact of unrest or protest movements also differs by the type of concerns, which are the central theme of these unrests. The protests or unrest motivated by socio-economic concerns often results in sharper GDP contractions as compared to those associated mainly with political concerns. Demonstrations which are triggered by a combination of both socio-economic and political factors tend to have the biggest impact.

Even in India there were instances especially in the protests against the Farm Laws, wherein, it was reported that some of '*anarchists masquerading as protesters*' had blocked the way ensuring entry/exit to the warehouses of a Patiala based storage company, by putting its own locks on the entry/exit point. Due to this act of the 'alleged' protesters the Company was facing huge business losses, as it was not able to access its facility, in a proper manner. The Company approached the Apex Court to get directions issued to the Union of India as well as State of Punjab to relocate or remove the protesters who have occupied its warehouse at Patiala and to deploy adequate resources outside the site in question, ensuring free and safe ingress and egress of the products of the three companies and also of the workers/employees and other persons, to and from the said storage facility.⁷⁵ A Bench led by Justice UU Lalit had refused to entertain

⁷⁴ Metodij Hadzi-Vaskov, Samuel Pienknagura, and Luca Ricci, Could Renewed Social Unrest Hinder the Recovery? (IMFBlog Chart of the Week, 13 July 2021), <https://blogs.imf.org/2021/07/13/could-renewed-social-unrest-hinder-the-recovery/>.

⁷⁵ Areeb Uddin Ahmed and Debayan Roy, "Anarchists masquerading as protesters:" Patiala based storage company moves Supreme Court against farm law protesters occupying its warehouse (Bar and Bench Litigation

the petition and instead granted liberty to the company to file the petition before the Punjab and Haryana High Court pursuant to which the Petitioners approached the Punjab & Haryana High Court. Before the Single Judge Bench of the High Court the petitioner company pleaded that it was suffering a loss amounting to more than one crore rupees on a daily basis due this illegal blockade being made before the warehouse. Furthermore, the Bench was also apprised of the fact that the warehouse contained items amounting to nearly 20 crore, which were perishable in nature.⁷⁶

Also in a similar plea⁷⁷ Punjab and Haryana High Court remarked that upholding the principle of “malice towards none with charity for all”, a solution must be reached out by the stakeholders as it is not simply a law and order problem, and Courts are battling to reconcile the competing rights and interests of all the stakeholders. In this matter as well a blockade was made outside a warehouse, by the protestors, thereby preventing the petitioners the access to the warehouse containing around about eight thousand metric tonnes of food-grains. The Court being mindful of the fact that any kind of wastage or loss to the food-grains could not be afforded by a country like ours and ordered that the state authorities must act expeditiously to end the stalemate so as to prevent any further losses in legal as well as economical terms to the stakeholders.

10. CONCLUDING REMARKS

On a concluding note the authors are of the view that if the dictum laid down in the *Amit Sahni* case⁷⁸ is followed in future, it will have many consequences. Firstly, if this dictum be used in the strikes or peaceful agitations carried out in the industrial sector as well, it would upset the industrial jurisprudence. Secondly, the State being in a powerful position will use this as a tool to suppress the views of a certain section of citizens who are not supporting the views of the government. This will pave the way for the State to not to engage with the protestors in a

News, 9 March 2021) <https://www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/storehouse-with-adani-goods-moves-supreme-court-against-farm-law-protesters-occupying-warehouse>.

⁷⁶ Areeb Uddin Ahmed, Punjab & Haryana High Court seeks response from Central, Punjab govts. in plea by storage company to remove Farm Law protesters from its warehouse (Bar and Bench Litigation News, 16 March 2021), <https://www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/punjab-haryana-high-court-notice-central-punjab-governments-storage-company-remove-protesting-farmers>.

⁷⁷ *Adani Wilmar Limited & Another v. State of Punjab & Others*, Civil Writ Petition No. 5645 of 2021, Decided on 18 June 2021.

⁷⁸ *Supra* note 62.

dialogue but rather to initiate prosecution against them.⁷⁹ In reality, the concept of ‘*Protests at a designated place*’ dilutes the concept of the protests⁸⁰ because it denies the protestors a place from where they can make the general public aware of the issues & causes for which they are protesting. The same was even contended during the hearing of the petitions concerning farm laws. The Apex Court should clarify the position of law in these aspects as there is a review petition filed against the *Shaheen Bagh* judgement⁸¹ pending before it, as the right to assemble peacefully without arms is also restricted by this judgement. Madras High Court in a case before it denied permission to carry out protest by the way of hunger strike at Marina Beach and observed that a citizen has no fundamental right to insist that his speech should be heard by an unwilling fellow citizen. Similarly, it is not possible to compel a person to witness a procession, against his wishes.⁸² At the same time, the freedom of speech and expression forms an integral part of the public meeting, hence any law which regulates this aspect of the public meeting can impose restrictions enshrined under Article 19(2)⁸³ in addition to those mentioned in Article 19(3)⁸⁴ & Article 19(5).⁸⁵ The Apex Court should apply the dicta laid down in *Asha Ranjan v. State of Bihar*⁸⁶ wherein it ruled that while balancing the rights of two sections of society the court should avoid such approach where the right of a particular section is completely extinct as it qualifies as prioritising one section over another. It has also been observed by the Court that any particular fundamental right of an individual cannot exist in isolation in a watertight compartment. One fundamental right of a person may have to coexist in harmony with the exercise of another fundamental right by others and also with a reasonable and a valid exercise of power by the State in the light of the directive principles in the interests of social welfare as a whole. It is the Court’s duty to strike a balance between competing claims of different interests and adjudicating the matter accordingly.⁸⁷ As the Apex Court in a case

⁷⁹ Debayan Roy, Supreme Court judgment on Shaheen Bagh protests “judicial sanction” for “police excesses”: Review petition in SC (Bar and Bench Litigation News, 16 November 2020), www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/supreme-court-shaheen-bagh-judgment-right-protest-review-petition-police.

⁸⁰ Propositions Like Holding Protests At ‘Designated Places Alone’ Shall Upset The Concept Of Dissent: Review Petition In Supreme Court Against Shaheen Bagh Judgement (Live Law News Network, 16 November 2020), www.livelaw.in/top-stories/propositions-like-holding-protests-at-designated-places-alone-shall-upset-the-concept-of-dissent-review-petition-in-supreme-court-against-shaheen-bagh-judgemnt-165912.

⁸¹ Supra note 62.

⁸² The Government of Tamil Nadu and Others v. P. Ayyakannu, W.A. No. 1042 of 2018; C.M.P. No. 8772 of 2018.

⁸³ Supra note 7.

⁸⁴ Supra note 8.

⁸⁵ INDIA CONST. art. 19, cl. 5.

⁸⁶ *Asha Ranjan v. State of Bihar*, (2017) 4 SCC 397.

⁸⁷ *Acharya Maharajshri Narandraprasadji Anandprasadji Maharaj v. State of Gujarat and Others*, AIR 1974 SC 2098.

has ruled out that no constitutional right can be claimed to be absolute in a realm where the rights are interconnected to each other, and limiting some rights in public interest might therefore be justified.⁸⁸ Another striking feature of these agitations was that not only a large number of women participated in the protests but also took the lead in certain instances.⁸⁹ We must keep that in mind that the courtroom remarks of the bench on the matter of composition of protestors on Farm Laws⁹⁰ convey a clear departure from the advanced thinking as they may be termed as regressive in their approach, as they seek to deny to more than half of the population the rights guaranteed to them under the *suprema lex*. If the remarks were made in the apprehension of the prevailing pandemic and the weather conditions⁹¹, they could be justified as they seem to address a concern which is humanitarian in nature, but if the intention is not that, then one cannot imagine that what kind of new Pandora's box will open regarding the chequered jurisprudence relating to right to protest available to the citizens of this country.

In the end, we are reminded of a Sanskrit shloka which goes as '*yadapi shuddham, loka viruddham na adaranyam, na acharanyam*' the meaning of which is even if an act is performed in good faith but if that harms the public interest then it should be avoided. Thereby, this dictum is not only applicable to the conduct of individuals but also to the actions of the state and its instrumentalities alike.

⁸⁸ Modern Dental College & Research Centre v. State of Madhya Pradesh, (2016) 7 SCC 353.

⁸⁹ Navjotpal Kaur and Sumeet Sekhon, Women take lead roles in India's farmer protest (The Conversation, 7 January 2021), <https://theconversation.com/women-take-lead-roles-in-indias-farmers-protest-151981>.

⁹⁰ "We Will Protects The Farmers' Land"- Supreme Court- Hearing On Farm Laws And Farmers Protest: Live-Updates (LiveLaw News Network, 12 January 2021), www.livelaw.in/top-stories/farm-laws-and-farmers-protest-live-updates-from-supreme-court-168294.

⁹¹ SC 'concerned' over old farmers, women protesting in cold, pandemic; CJI asks them to go home (The Week, 11 January, 2021), www.theweek.in/news/india/2021/01/11/sc-concerned-over-old-farmers-women-protesting-in-cold-pandemic-cji-asks-them-to-go-home.html.